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A NEW METHOD OF UNDERWATER COMPOSITE IMPACT TESTING

Authors: Rowan L. Caldwell¹, Matthew J. Donough¹, Gleny T. Chirima², Alban Robin³, Andrew W. Phillips², Nigel A. St John², B. Gangadhara Prusty¹

¹ ARC Training Centre for Automated Manufacture of Advanced Composites, School of Mechanical & Manufacturing Engineering, UNSW Sydney, NSW 2052, Australia

² Maritime Division, Defence Science and Technology Group, Port Melbourne, VIC 3207, Australia

³Advanced Structural Materials and Hyperbaric Testing Laboratory (SMASH), Ifremer, Centre de Bretagne, Plouzané, France

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Does it work with the existing impact system?

06

OLD COUPON

Does it work with traditional coupons?

07

NEW COUPON

Does it work with a new coupon design?

08

CONCLUSIONS

What contributions are made to the field?

DURABILITY OF COMPOSITE PROPELLERS

This work was conducted as part of a UNSW PhD degree in association with the Durability of Composite Propellers project, an international joint research effort between UNSW AMAC CRC (AU), DSTG (AU), IFREMER (FR) and DGA (FR).

WHY?

Water decreases damage

HAMPSON, P.R. AND MOATAMEDI, M., 2010

Damage area decreased for wet impacts due to reduced peak impact force.

KWON, Y. AND CONNER, R., 2012

Damage area increased for wet impacts due to increased peak impact force

Water increases damage

WHY?

HAMPSON, P.R. AND MOATAMEDI, M., 2010

KWON, Y. AND CONNER, R., 2012

WHY?

**LABORATORY-SCALE,
INSTRON INTEGRATED,
UNDERWATER IMPACT SYSTEM,
METHODOLOGY AND RESULTS**

WHAT?

INTEGRATES WITH INSTRON

SEALED PERSPEX VIEWING WINDOW

INSTALLATION = 20 MIN

TANK FILING = 5 MIN

COUPON EXCHANGE = 30 SEC

TANK EMPTY = 5 MIN

WHAT?

- Red marks indicate the time of water entry.
- No difference in dry (air) and wet (UW) velocity profiles during water entry or just prior to coupon impact.
- Energy absorption of water damping increased with impact energy

!MOH

 Designation: D7136/D7136M - 15

10 Standard Test Method for Measuring the Damage Resistance of a Fiber-Reinforced Polymer Matrix Composite to a Drop-Weight Impact Event¹

OLD COUPON

D7136 COUPON

NEW COUPON

NEW COUPON

NEW COUPON

Added mass factor:

$$\frac{\omega_{uw}}{\omega_{air}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \beta}}$$

$$\beta = \left(\frac{\omega_{air}}{\omega_{uw}} \right)^2 - 1$$

NEW COUPON

HAMPSON ET AL

KWON, OWENS ET AL

CALDWELL ET AL

DISCUSSION

1. EQUIPMENT

An existing, standardised and calibrated drop tower was retrofitted with a tank inside the impact chamber and successfully used for underwater impact testing in a traditional laboratory environment.

2. METHOD

The ASTM D7136 standard of composite impact testing is unsuitable for assessment of the impact performance of submerged laminates as submersion has an insignificant effect on impact response and impact tolerance.

3. COUPON

A larger, 300x300mm² coupon design was found to offer sufficient compliance to reliably measure the change in impact response and impact resistance of submerged laminates as opposed to laminates in air.

4. FSI EFFECT

The added mass factor was 6.1 +/- 0.8 for 10J impacts and 7.6 +/- 0.6 for 20J impacts. Impact damage areas for submerged laminates were 60% smaller than for impacts in air due to approximately 30% reductions in submerged peak impact forces.

CONCLUSIONS

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THANKS

Does anyone have any questions?

rowanc111@gmail.com

+61 4 5738 1690

<https://www.linkedin.com/in/r-caldwell/>

